

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Measurement of the distribution, localization, and growth trend of economic activities

SPOKE 4 - RM2 - Competitiveness of economic activities and valorization of natural and cultural assets in mountain and remote areas

DELIVERABLE D2.0

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework - NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping,

testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A) Measurement of the distribution, localization, and growth trend of economic activities

Objectives description

Mapping the existing economic activities within the rural mountain areas and the interrelationships among them. The measurements range from different economic domains, including nature-based tourism and cultural sector. Mapping will be designed to help communities and public policy makers to implement digital and innovative solutions based on direct involvement of local actors.

Summary of the activities

Identification of mountain municipalities within the different Valleys and Mountain Unions, municipalities were analyzed for the following Valleys: Valtournenche, Valsavarenche, Valpelline, Valle Varaita, Valle Orco, Valgrisenche, Val Soana, Val Pellice, Val di Rhêmes, Val di Cogne, Val d'Ayas, Saint Nicolas, Plaine di Aosta and the following mountain unions: Unité des Communes valdôtaines Grand-Paradis, Unité des Communes valdôtaines Evançon, Unités des Communes valdôtaines Grand-Combin, Unité des Communes valdôtaines Mount-Emilius, Unité des Communes valdôtaines Mont-Emilius, Unité des Communes valdôtaines Mont-Cervin, Unione Montana dei Comunes del Monviso, Unione Montana Gran Paradiso, Unione Montana del Pinerolese.

Following the municipality identification, we looked for economic and tourism related information and data for the creation of a database able to map the economic trends and diversity in the valleys. Firstly, have been identified the number of activities opened in the years from 2009 to 2021, we collected from Italian Camera di Commercio database the number of active companies for each year divided by ATECO code down to the second digit (e.g., ATECO A 01 - Agricultural crops and production of animal products). Starting from the literature about tourism we have then identified and searched economic and tourism related indicators for each municipality, the data are Population, Area, Rate of employment/unemployment, Touristic arrivals, Infrastructure (road - railways), Number of schools, Waste produced, Pro capita income.

Outputs

The output of the activities is a panel organized database that contains all the municipalities in the analyzed areas stated above, organized for their

respective valley of belonging. For each of these municipality the database contains observations for each year from 2009 to 2021. The variables observed in the database are:

- Number of active companies divided per ATECO (ISTAT)
- Population(ISTAT)
- Area(ISTAT)
- Population density (ISTAT)
- Touristic classification(ISTAT)
- Infrastructure (kilometers of road within the municipality)(ISTAT)
- Number of schools(ISTAT)
- Rate of unemployment(MEF)
- Pro capita income (MEF)
- Total income (MEF)
- Number of taxpayers (MEF)

There are 819 observations in the dataset corresponding of 63 municipalities analyzed in 13 years (2009-2021). 25 Municipalities are in Valle d'Aosta region and 38 in Piemonte region, of them 14 are in Cuneo province and the remaining 24 in Torino province. All the data have been collected on the open databases of ISTAT (Istituto Nazionale di Statistica Italiano, <https://www.istat.it>), MEF (Ministero dell' Economia e delle Finanze, <https://www.mef.gov.it>) and Camera di Commercio (<https://www.camcom.it>).

With the dataset is possible to perform analyses ranging from basic descriptive analysis on the trend of companies active during the years per municipality, to econometric analyses comparing different valleys with similar economic/tourist indicators and controlling the performance of various municipality to understand the possible causes that may lead to some of them to perform well and other to see economic decline in the recent years.